

Reflection Properties of the Human Skin From 14 to 42 GHz

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Abstract

With the rollout of 5G in frequency range 2 (FR2) mm-wave in the 26.5 to 30 GHz range in various countries as well as a raft of EU projects addressing health risks of 5G FR2 there is a requirement to enhance the knowledge base on skin reflection properties. In 2021 an extensive study was published by Christ et al, however, the lowest measurement frequency was 40 GHz, this is above the highest mm-wave 5G frequencies currently in use. This study fills in the gap presenting reflection measurements from 14 to 42 GHz. The knowledge is of importance in the conversion from incident power density to absorbed power density and in many measurement applications and phantoms for over the air performance measurement. In addition to reflection measurements optical coherence tomography was performed on the same skin areas to allow accurate geometric skin models to be generated for use in the accompanying simulations enabling extraction of skin layer dielectric properties.

Introduction

With the rollout of 5G in frequency range 2 (FR2), specifically mm-wave in the 24.25 to 29.5 GHz range, across various countries, as well as a raft of EU projects addressing health risks of 5G FR2, there is a requirement to enhance the knowledge base on skin reflection properties. In 2021 an extensive study was published by Christ et al, however, the lowest measurement frequency was 40 GHz, well above the highest 5G frequencies currently in use. Studies by Alekseev et al (2008) and Alekseev et al (2007) looked at skin dosimetry and skin permittivity respectively, however only at higher frequencies, in this case above 30 GHz. This study fills in the gap presenting reflection measurements from 14 to 42 GHz. This knowledge is of importance in the conversion from incident power density to absorbed power density as well as in many measurement applications and in the design of phantoms for over the air performance measurement.

Methods

Measurements were performed using a one port network analyser, an Anritsu MS46131A, and open ended waveguides packed with low dielectric constant Rohacell HF51 to prevent the skin from intruding into the waveguide and keep the skin surface flat. The network analyser has a coaxial output which is converted to waveguide using end launch transitions from Eravant. The two waveguides used are listed in table 1 along with their frequency ranges and dimensions. Lower frequencies were not measured as the waveguide opening becomes too large to allow consistent skin contact.

Name	Frequency Range	Cutoff Frequency	Cutoff next mode	A mm	B mm
WR42	18.00 to 26.50 GHz	14.051 GHz	28.102 GHz	10.668	4.318
WR28	26.50 to 40 GHz	21.077 GHz	42.154 GHz	7.112	3.556

Prior to the measurement of the skin, the network analyser / waveguide combination was calibrated using WR-28 VNA or WR-42 VNA waveguide calibration kits from Eravant, the calibration plane is the flange face that contacts the skin. Figure 1 shows the setup with WR-28, the Rohacellis clearly visible inside the

waveguide. Waveguide reflection coefficients were measured in a group of 35 male and female volunteers of different age groups. All measurements were performed on the skin immediately after being cleaned with soap and water and dried with a towel. For each subject, measurements were taken at 15 different skin locations with three measurements per location, Figure 2. These locations were selected based on the previous study by Christ et al, but excluding 6 positions that proved very difficult to obtain consistent data for due to body or facial hair. These locations represented regions of either thin or thick stratum corneum.

Figure 1. Anritsu vector network analyser with open ended waveguide attached

Figure 2. Illustration of the 17 body locations on the hand, arm, and forehead at which the S_{11} of the human volunteers were measured.

In a smaller group, both S11 measurements and optical coherence tomography (OCT) was performed at a few selected locations. The OCT allows a detailed model of the superficial skin layers to be generated. Simulations using the FDTD solver in SIM4LIFE 8.2 including the waveguide measurement setup and the skin model enables the skin layer properties to be optimised to provide the best match to the measured data.

Using simulations, the guided wave reflection coefficients can be used to determine the effective composite dielectric constant from which the plane wave free space reflection coefficient can be determined. Due to the nature of the guided wave wavelength and its non-linear function of frequency.

Results

The measurement results and analysis will be presented at the conference.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057622 (Project "Scientific-based Exposure and risk Assessment of radiofrequency and mm-Wave systems from children to elderly (5G and Beyond)"-SEAWave), and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

References

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